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Women Access to and Ownership of Land in Sokoto Metropolis, North-Western Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined women access to and ownership of public land grant in Sokoto metropolis. Primary data was mainly collected through documented records of applications for land and actual allocations (grants) made from 2000–2023 by the State Government through the Ministry for Land and Housing. In addition information was obtained from 212 sampled women who were granted plots of land using structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics, percentages and ratios were used for data analysis. The study revealed that majority of the sampled women have access to traditional Islamic education system and engage in formal sector employment. They were of medium to high socio-economic status. The commonest means of access to land in the study area is inheritance from close relatives and public grants. It found that none of the legal documents both religious/statutory prevents women from access to land in the study area. It was even discovered that women applications during the study period stand at 12.9%. Result from the actual land grants revealed that over the thirty year period, majority (86%) of the beneficiaries of public land allocations were mostly men compared to women beneficiaries (- 15%) . Despite the value they attached to land ownership, few of the women show desire to own land due to lack of awareness and enlightenment. It was also discovered that political participation and level of formal education and socio-cultural practices were influential factors influencing actual access to land grants. The study concluded that these practices combine with inadequate awareness prevent women from access to public land grants in the study area. Therefore, it recommends that the State Government should make public land and housing grants procedures public through the local media. The State Government should give emphasis to women’s literacy and skills acquisition to enhance their access to information as well as income earning productive activities particularly for married women. Women groups should put women sensitization part of their agenda among others.

Keywords: women groups, public land grant, political participation

1. INTRODUCTION

In most developing countries, land is not only the primary means for generating a livelihood but often the main vehicle for investing, accumulating wealth, and transferring it between generations. Thus, the ways in which access to land is regulated, property rights are defined, and ownership conflicts are resolved has broad implications beyond the sphere of agricultural production (Deininger and Binswanger, 1999). Women represent a large segment of the society who relied on land for income generation in the developing countries and they contribute a lot to local economy by generating income for themselves and others. Notwithstanding, they still represent a minority in terms of access and benefits from land ownership. Women across the developing countries faced a number of barriers to accessing public resources such as land, housing, credit, training, information as well as political policy constraints

(Bandura, 1999). Studies shows that there little progress in narrowing the gap between men and women in access to benefits from public resources.

In Nigeria, gender plays a critical role in land ownership, women are perceived as unequal players, status and economic sectors compared to men. There is the need to consider the effect of socio-cultural factors in a patriarchal social system and its impact on women's perception to land issues. The patriarchal societal system already subjugates women right and improving their land tenure will be an avenue to improve their economic value. Interestingly, the women in the study area already have a conservative attitude towards land issues and would rather decline from land issues than get involved. Kleinbooi and Lahiff (2007 cited in George, *et al.*, 2014) agrees to this and traced women's conservativeness to the patriarchal system of land holding. They also found that few women were willing to challenge the highly gendered nature of land rights in a traditional society. Many Nigerian communities still operate the traditional and family inheritance system of land ownership that gives preference to male children.

By law, urban land in the country is owned by state governments, and control over them is exercised by the 36 governors. In urban areas of Nigeria only 4.5 percent of the women have access to land while 49.5 percent of men own land. Amongst the urban poor population, 5.9 percent of the women have land compared to 28 per cent of their male counterparts (George *et al.*, 2014). Access to and benefits from public land is an issue that affect both male and female in most societies but the benefits is highly skewed in favour of men. As a result women's socio-economic development is highly hampered due to inadequate access to productive resources particularly in Nigeria where they constituted majority of the poor. Women also shoulder many family obligations despite their limited resources (Nuratu and Mairo, 2022). Extensive studies have been carried out on women contributions to household and national economy, especially in the area of agriculture and food security (Enete and Amusa, 2010; Sofa Team and Doss, 2011). One area that lacks adequate research is gender access and ownership rights to urban land and its implication on the women social security. Even though theoretically, the Nigerian land use Act of 1978 gives men and women equal right to access and own land, in practical terms, women unlike their male counterparts are handicapped by many socio-economic and cultural factors. More so, the location of this study in a traditional northern city presents an insightful contribution to the discourse on the extent to which women have access to urban land. Sokoto town which is the focus of this study is the capital of Sokoto State. The town has grown to be an important regional commercial Centre in the North Western Nigeria. The urban lands are used for residential, commercial and other livelihood activities.

The aim of this study is to examine the extent to which women desire ownership and benefits from land grant. The specific objectives are:

- (a) Identify trends and the extent to which women desire land grant through applications.
- (b) To find out the trends and extent to which women benefits from land grant in Sokoto.
- (c) To identify and explain some of the benefits and barriers to women's access to land if any.

1.2 Research Hypotheses

The research intend to test the hypotheses is stated as bellow;

H₀, there is no significant difference in the number hectares granted to men and women applicants

2.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 The Study Area

Sokoto is the capital of Sokoto State of Nigeria, it is situated at the north west of the confluence of the Rima and Sokoto Rivers (plate 1). This area is located between latitude 12⁰ and 14⁰ N longitude 4⁰ and 6⁰ E (Benna Associates, 1985 and Mamman, 1999). This area has been defined by Sokoto Urban Regional Planning Board (SURPB) as that which is described by a 16km radius centred on the Old Race Course. The area was further extended later to include several critical outlying villages that have a socio-economic dependence upon the town of Sokoto. This "region" or the inner close-settled zone is about 960 square kilometre in area (Benna Associates, 1985). Administratively, this area falls within six Local Government jurisdictions, namely Sokoto North, Sokoto South, Dange - Shuni, Kware and Wamakko (Danmalam, 2010). For the purpose of this study, Sokoto urban area / Metropolis is define as all wards in Sokoto North, Sokoto South, Parts of Wamakko and Dange-Shuni LGAs. The urban area is mainly

populated by people of Hausa/Fulani ethnic group who were largely Muslims, with significant minority ethnic groups from South West, South East as well as middle belt of Nigeria. The major occupations of the people are commercial trading activities involving secondary and tertiary services.

Plate 1: Sokoto Urban area

2.2 Sampling procedure and sampling size

This study consist of two parts, the first part consist of data from obtained from land documents in the State Ministry of Lands and Housing. This consist of records of applications for land and list of persons who were granted plots land approved by the State Government between 2000 and 2023. In addition list of housing allocations made by Sokoto State Government during the same period was also used. The second part is the list of 212 women who were allocated land during the period. These women were identified and information collected from them using structured questionnaire.

2.3 Instruments of Data Collection

Data for this study were collected from official records of State Ministry of Lands and Housing to examine trends and gender access to public grants. First, the number of applications submitted by both men and women for plots of land was obtained from records of Ministry for Land between the year 2000 and 2023 (Table 1). And also, the number of hectares land allocated to persons which were 513.9 hectares granted to both men and women. The two hundred and twelve women 212, who were granted plots of land were purposively profiled and Structured Questionnaires (SQs) was used to collect information from them on issues relating to land acquisition and management. Qualitative data were gathered via books, journal articles, and web-based materials among others.

Table 1: Number of Applicants by Gender from 2000-2023

Years	Male Applications	Female Applications	Total Applications
2000-2005	1694	137	1831
2006-2011	2420	312	2732
2012-2017	2604	438	3042
2018-2023	2804	635	3439
Total	9522	1522	11044

Sokoto State Ministry for Land and Housing

2.4 Method of Data Presentation and Analysis

The data was presented and analysed by the use of descriptive statistical tools such as tabulations, frequency distributions tables, percentages, ratio while chi-square was used to determine the influence of age, level of education, occupation and economic status on women's property ownership.

3.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Profile of the sampled women landowners

From the information in Table 2, it was found that significant majority (67%) of the respondents were adults above the age of 40, while the least were young adults less than 30 years old. This revealed the predominance of adult women in the sample. It shows that older women are more conscious of land ownership compared to younger ones. As regards marital status, more than half of the sampled women were married (59%), followed by widows and divorced. While the least (4.2%) were singles among the sampled respondents, the widows were likely to remarry (Table 2). Majority of the sampled respondents had some form of education as shown in the (table 2). Majority of the respondents have advance level education up to tertiary and university level. The least (6%) were those with only Islamic education. Although, even those with formal education must have attended Islamic school system.

The study revealed different activities as the main occupation of the women in the study area (Table 2). More than half of the respondents revealed that they were engage in formal employment in the public sector and its associated institutions. This is followed by those women who were engage in home based production while the least were those who engaged in service provision. None of the respondents were found in any agricultural employment in the study area. With regards to income earning among the women land owners, from Table 2, it was found that a good proportion of them were within the third income group, followed by those who earned between N61, 000-N80, 000. The least were those earning between N31, 000-N40, 000 monthly (Table 2). It was found that none of the respondents were earning less than N20, 000. Many of the respondents revealed that they were salary earners and of them do participate at one time or the other in informal saving among women (Adashi) out of the little family expenditure.

Table 2: Socio-Economic Profile of the Women Applicants

Age	Frequency	%
Less than 20	-	-
21 –30	29	13.6
31 - 40	40	18.9
41 –50	71	33.4
Above 50	72	34.4
Total	212	100
Marital status		
Married	125	59.0
Divorced	29	13.6
Widowed	49	23.1
Single	09	4.2
Total	212	100
Education status		
Islamic education only	13	6.1
Primary School only	25	11.7
Secondary school	62	29.2
Tertiary Education	81	38.2
University	31	14.6
Total	212	100
Occupation		
Petty trading and services	24	11.3
Production based	64	30.2
Civil servant	113	53.3
Service provision	11	5.2
Total	212	100
Average income		
Below -20,000	-	-
N21,000-40,000	19	8.9
N41,000-60,000	81	28.7
N61,000-80,000	66	27.8
Above -81,000	37	17.3
Total	212	100

Field work, 2023.

3.2 Trends in Demand for Urban land Grant in Sokoto metropolis

Demand for land is measured by the number of application submitted to the state Ministry of Land and Housing from 2000 to 2023. Table 3 gives a summary of the trends in demand for both residential and commercial land within the metropolis. The study show that in the first period, significant number (92.5%) of the applications for were submitted by male applicants while those submitted by women were few indeed (Table 3). There was steady increased in women applications between 2012-2017 and 2018-2023. This perhaps, might not to be unconnected with the awareness brought about by increase in the number of educated women civil servants and those involved in politics. Despite the above, the highest number of women applications stand at 14.3% and 18.4%.

The table revealed that, the percentage of women applicants throughout the study period were very low compared to the number of male applications (12.9%). From the table it can be seen that, out of the total applications submitted during the study period only 12.9% were submitted by women. The study revealed that for any eight male applications only one was from a female applicant (8:1). It appears that most of the women in the study area were not informed about the means to access land. Also, most of women who applied for land or housing might be educated and in the civil service or those who retired from service. This means that lack of formal education and awareness might be among the reasons why few of them

shows interest in acquiring land through the Government grant. The above is consistent with the findings from a study on women and land ownership in Ota (George, *et al.*, 2014).

Table 3: Applications for public land grants 2000-2023 (in hectares)

Years	Totals Applications	Male applications		Female applications		Male/Female Ratio
		Number	% of total	Number	% of total	
2000-2005	1831	1694	92.5	137	7.4	13:1
2006-2011	2732	2420	88.5	312	11.4	8:1
2012-2017	3042	2604	85.6	438	14.3	6:1
2018-2023	3439	2804	81.5	635	18.4	4:1
Total	11044	9522	87.0	1522	12.9	8:1

Sokoto State Ministry for Land and Housing, 2023

3.3 Trends in Urban land allocation in Sokoto Metropolis.

Government land allocation was measured from the number of grants to individuals approved by the State Government over the study period. The trend over the years was divided into four year period (table 4). The study revealed that in the first four years 2001 and 2003 significant proportion of the beneficiaries were males, it shows that out of any six hectares allocated only one was allocated to women beneficiaries. Then between year 2004 and 2007, about 90% of the grants were also in favour of male beneficiaries. In the third period 2008 and 2011, there was slight increase in the number of hectares approved for female beneficiaries (Table 5). This was followed by 2016 and 2019 period that also show improvement in women's share where they got 18% of the plots granted. Throughout the study period a total of 513.9 hectares of urban land in Sokoto was shared to beneficiaries, significant majority of the allocations were granted to male beneficiaries and only 13.1% of the land was actually given to women. Although, women's share increased over the period, the largest proportion of the grants were in favour of male beneficiaries.

In terms of land right, the law does not out-rightly discriminate on who owns the land based on gender (Aluko and Amidu, 2006). Discovery from the field survey shows that it's challenging for both genders to acquire land through public grant, particularly for low social status women in the study area. Also, from the records studied, it is obvious that minor forms of gender discrimination exist in the share of land grants. Although, this is not a general norm but most times, economic and political connections are prominent in determining who get what. It seems factors such as socio-economic, gender, and traditions has significant influence on the way land were allocated in the study area. The result shows consistency with a similar study on women, land and property rights in Benin City, Nigeria (Sumaina and Thobeka, 2018). Despite the stereotype and challenges in acquiring land, small number of educated women were able secure grant for themselves. This is similar to the findings from a study on women land ownership and participation in decision making about housing development in Oyo South-West Nigeria (Oshikoya and Ifediora, 2022).

Table 4: Trend in Urban land allocation in Sokoto metropolis 2009-2023

Years	Total Hectares Distributed	Allocated to males		Allocated to females		Male/female Ratio
		Number	% of total	Number	% of total	
2000–2003	82.6	69.1	83.6	13.5	16.3	5:1
2004–2007	78.5	70.7	90.0	7.8	9.9	9:1
2008–2011	13.1	131	85.8	18.1	13.9	6:1
2012–2015	52.9	46.8	88.4	6.1	11.5	7:1
2016-2019	119.7	98.0	81.8	21.7	18.1	4:1
2020-2023	48.3	44.4	91.9	3.9	8.0	12:1
TOTAL	513.9	442.8	86.9	71.1	13.1	7:1

Sokoto State Ministry for Land and Housing, 2023.

3.4 Benefits of land ownership to women

In order to understand the importance of land to women, two hundred and twelve women beneficiaries of land grant were purposively identified and interviewed using structured questionnaire. Table 5 revealed the various reasons given by the respondents to support their view that personal land / property is also important to women like men. The study shows that women in the study area perceived land ownership in different ways and this depends on their personal experience with regard to spousal and family relation. A good proportion of the women revealed that land or property is a source of income (Table 5). As a sources income from which they can engage in home based productive activities from their personal land. Another proportion of the women (36.3%) opined that personal property give them means to shoulder various family obligations. This is followed by those who suggested that personal property give them financial independence and frees them from dependence on others. The least were those who indicated that land is a means of social security to women. Evidence suggests that many of those who opted for land control and social security might have previous unhappy marriage/family relations that propelled them to strive for a land or house of their own, or they have a number of dependants that require personal care. The result is consistent to the findings from a study conducted in Ogun State, on women’s access to land and its implications for economic empowerment in Ota, Nigeria (George *et al.*, 2022)

Table 5: Benefits of land ownership to women

Benefits of landownership to women	Frequency	%
Source of income	85	40.1
Means of social security	11	5.2
Financial independence	39	18.4
For family obligations	77	36.3
Total	212	100

Field work, 2023.

3.5 Factors Influencing Women Access to Land

The respondents suggested a number of factors that hinders women from access to and ownership to land (Table 6). A good proportion of the respondents indicated that women have few income sources, meaning men were financially better compared to women. This is followed by those who suggested that custom and tradition in the study area favour men more than women when it comes to access to land. Table 6.0 revealed that, least were those who suggested that illiteracy and lack of awareness is a factor that hinders women from seeking or aspiring for land ownership. The table shows the challenges against women is centered on the traditional believes and custom practices together with poverty. Illiteracy is also discovered to be another issue affecting women. Therefore, these factors should be expected to limit their desire to apply for urban land grant and housing. The study result is consistent with the findings of a study in Oyo South-West, on the issues affecting women access to land and housing (Oshikoya and Ifediora, 2022).

Table 6: Barriers to women access to land

Factors	Frequency	%
Tradition & custom	71	33.4
Male dominance	37	17.4
Illiteracy	32	15.0
Low income	72	33.9
Total	212	100

Field work, 2023

4.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study was carried out in order to find out whether women whether desire to acquire urban land and benefits from government land grant in Sokoto Metropolis, It has been established through the findings of the study that the Land Use Act of 1979, does not discriminates between genders in terms of access to and control over land. But findings from this study shows that social status, traditions and customs play critical roles in access to land grant by women. It was also discovered that the common perception of many women in the study area is that it is men who need land most compared women. The result has highlighted the fact that gender discrimination in access to and ownership of urban land in Sokoto remains a social problem that affect both genders. But inadequate represented in the decision making process may likely be one of the reasons for their smaller share in land distribution. The significance of land as asocial security net cannot be overemphasized. Therefore, women access to land will result in economic empowerment, especially because it will avail them the opportunity to earn extra income and even securing loans from financial institutions. This study recommends the adoption of an all-inclusive approach to deal with the effects of gender discrimination in access to land on women. That women should be given representation in the land use and allocation committee.

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